

COMPARATIVE CLASSIFICATION AND CONTENT OF MUKYMI'S WORKS.

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ABSTRACT

In this article, it is shown that Muhammed Aminkhoja Mukymi did not abandon his creative path despite the difficulties in his life and that he is considered one of the poets who brought out justice and revealed truths in his work. the development of the literature of that period and its interests and classifications mainly in comics are shown. A few examples of his creativity are given in the social and economic spheres. He lived with hope for the future.

Muhammad Aminkhoja Mukymi is one of the writers who had an admirable and exemplary life path, who was able to make a great contribution to the formation of society in a certain period, and who has a deep place in the hearts of the people. Muhammad Aminkhoja Mukymi is one of the great writers and has led an exemplary life. In his works, he created not only an artistic interpretation, but also expressed his views on economic views and state management, which can serve as an example for today's generation. Mukymi was one of the people who was rich not materially, but spiritually. If attention is paid to his personal life path, it is possible to study the way of life that can be an example from him. Based on the study of Mukymi's works, it is possible to observe and analyze the economic situation in the country during this period. Based on the study of the works, it is possible to see economic aspects that can be applied even today. In addition, in his works, Mukymi mentioned the personality of the leaders and the important factors that the people demand from them. Despite the fact that this period was a difficult period, Mukymi was able to fearlessly criticize the administration system and the country's tax system in his works. In addition, the geographical situation of the country and the social situation of the regions can be studied from the works. The standard of living of the population is also mentioned in the works.

He made contacts and creatively collaborated with advanced artists such as Almai and Nodim. The literary life of the period when Mukymi lived and worked was complicated. Such an environment had a strong influence on Mukymi's work. In the early period of his work, there are elements of formalism, indulgence in artistic inclinations. But he quickly gave up such traditions and looked critically at the evils in society and old beliefs. He learned from Navoi, Nizami, and Fuzuli, who attached ghazals to their ghazals. He considered Jomiy to be his mentor. He continued the traditions of Uzbek and Persian classical poets. The emergence and

formation of the democratic direction in Uzbek literature is connected with the name of Mukymi. Such forward-thinking poets as Chief Furqat, Zavqi, Avaz, Kamil opened a new page in the history of Uzbek literature. Mukymi's lyrics are imbued with deep optimism, vitality is one of the main and leading features of these lyrics.¹ Based on the impressions of his trips to different cities and villages, he wrote 4-part "Travel" work. The work is written in a light, playful tone and consists of four line stanzas. It realistically depicts the hardships of people's lives and the destruction of villages. The poet approved the good, praised the beauty, laughed at the shortcomings and reprimanded, criticized the evil and various vices. Mukymi's letters in prose and verse are examples of epistolary literature. 10 poetic and about 20 prose letters have been saved. His poems have come down to us in manuscripts, poems, books published in lithography at the beginning of the 20th century, and in the pages of contemporary press printed in Tashkent and Petersburg².

The permanent national renaissance gave rise to the "Sayohatnoma" genre in Uzbek literature. It depicted the burdens imposed by the tsarist government on the people due to the conflicts of the time, fierce criticism of the ruling of the tyrant and unjust governor, and the ruined and destroyed villages. The poet's "Sayohatnoma" was studied by experts at the time¹. A comparison of the text of „Sayohatnoma” in current editions with the original and close versions shows that there are many textual differences in them. This, in its own power, had a serious impact on the interpretation of the work. However, they do not fully express Mukymi's worldview, his point of view towards a certain reality, and sometimes they give the opposite impression. The study of Muqimi's work began during his lifetime. This includes debates and articles about various relationships expressed in his poems will be evidence. It should be noted that it is a literary classic in the literary-historical heritage of the Uzbek people works occupy an important place. Such works, our heritage, are true study, their scientific analysis is one of the urgent tasks of our day. Muhammad Aminkhoja's life path was not easy and luxurious, however, he remained faithful to his creative path. He wrote many humorous satires. In particular, he revealed the evils and justice of that time. I conclude that if Muhammed Aminkhoja did not stop his creativity even in difficult times, we should also work tirelessly in this time of global development and contribute to the development of the country. In addition, we should make maximum use of all the opportunities given by the head of our country.

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